

Liver PPI

Compare Outcomes Analysis

Introduction

TriNetX is the global federated health research network providing access to electronic medical records (diagnoses, procedures, medications, laboratory values, genomic information) across large healthcare organizations (HCOs). This report was run on the set of HCOs grouped into a network called Research. This network included 76 HCO(s).

This report describes a Compare Outcomes Analysis, named ALD Outcomes balance lab/med 1.13.23, generated by the TriNetX platform on Jan 13, 2023, 18:08:20 UTC. This analysis compared the outcomes of two cohorts: Cohort A (9,641 patients) named *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23 and Cohort B (13,394 patients) named *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23.

Methods

The analysis process includes two main steps: 1) Defining the cohorts through query criteria; 2) Setting up and running the analysis. Setting up the analysis requires definitions for the index event, outcomes criteria, and the time frame. Compare outcomes supports four analyses: Measures of Association, Survival, Number of Instances and Lab result distribution. These analyses have additional options that are listed in the Outcomes Definitions and Analyses Specifications section below. Furthermore, characteristics of the cohorts that are balanced using propensity score matching are also included in the Propensity Score Matching section.

Cohorts definition

This section lists all terms used in the definitions of the two cohorts.

Query Criteria for Cohort 1 (query name: *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23)

This query was run on the network Research with 76 HCO(s) queried and 76 HCO(s) responded. A total of 59 provider(s) responded with patients. The final cohort included 9,641 patients who matched the query criteria listed in the table below. For the text representation of the query criteria please see Appendix A.

Ungrouped terms				
must have	demographics	Age	Age (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence))	
cannot have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01	Wilson's disease	
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01	Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0	Cholangitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3	Primary biliary cirrhosis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19	Viral hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
Group 1				
Group 1A Alc CIR				
must have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (at least 18 years old at event)	
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019			
event relationship	Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR			
Group 1B				

must have	any of	medication medication medication medication medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346 NLM:RXNORM:283742 NLM:RXNORM:17128 NLM:RXNORM:40790 NLM:RXNORM:7646	dexlansoprazole esomeprazole lansoprazole pantoprazole Omeprazole
Group 2				
Group 2A				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (at least 18 years old at event)
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of Group 2B occurred on or before any instance of Group 2A		
Group 2B				
cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites

Query Criteria for Cohort 2 (query name: *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23)

This query was run on the network Research with 76 HCO(s) queried and 76 HCO(s) responded. A total of 58 provider(s) responded with patients. The final cohort included 13,394 patients who matched the query criteria listed in the table below.

Ungrouped terms				
must have		demographics	Age	Age (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence))
cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01	Wilson's disease
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01	Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0	Cholangitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3	Primary biliary cirrhosis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19	Viral hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
Group 1				
Group 1A Alc CIR				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (at least 18 years old at event)
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR		
Group 1B				
cannot have		medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole
Group 2				
Group 2A				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (at least 18 years old at event)
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of Group 2B occurred on or before any instance of Group 2A		
Group 2B				

cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites

Analysis Setup

This section contains the Index Event and Time Window definitions and a list of selected outcomes and the analyses.

Index Event & Time Window Definitions

The index event defines the point in time when each patient in the cohort enters the analysis. To define an index event for the cohort, one or more criteria for the cohort must be selected. The index date for each patient within a cohort is the day on which the patient first met the selected criteria for the cohort (listed in the table below).

As the index event defines the earliest time point after which outcomes are analyzed, the time window defines the duration during which outcomes are analyzed. The time window can start on the same day as the index event or at any specified time interval after the index event. The time window can end any time after the start date. Outcomes are defined as diagnoses, medications, procedures, or laboratory values that happened in the time window starting after the first occurrence of the index event.

Time Window Used in this Analysis

This analysis included outcomes that occurred in the time window that started on the same day as the first occurrence of the index event and ended 1095 days after the first occurrence of the index event

The index event only includes events that occurred up to 20 years ago. Patients whose index event occurred 20 years or more ago are excluded. In this analysis, 0 patients in Cohort 1 and 0 patients in Cohort 2 were excluded because they met the index event more than 20 years ago.

Index Events Used in this Analysis

Index events for the Compare Outcomes analysis were derived from the cohort definitions. Index events were defined separately for each cohort and were based on the criteria used in the original cohort definition. Please see Appendix B for the text representation of the index event definition.

The index event for Cohort 1 (query name: *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23) was defined as the following:

Group 1				
Group 1A Alc CIR				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (at least 18 years old at event)
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019			
event relationship	Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR			
Group 1B				
must have	any of	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

The index event for Cohort 2 (query name: *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23) was defined as the following:

Group 1			
Group 1A Alc CIR			
must have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (at least 18 years old at event)
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship	Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR		
Group 1B			
cannot have	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646
			Omeprazole

Analyses Specifications

The Compare Outcomes Analytic supports four types of analyses: Measure of Association, Survival, Number of Instances, and Lab result distribution. The first three analyses support the “exclude patients with outcomes prior to the window” setting. This option can exclude patients from the analysis if they are not at risk for an outcome (e.g., if the outcome is a chronic disease). When "exclude patients with the outcome prior to the time window" is not checked, all patients in the cohort are included in the analysis, regardless of whether they had the outcome prior to the time window. When "exclude patients with the outcome prior to the time window" is checked, patients are excluded from the analysis if their record includes the outcome prior to the beginning of the time window. This selection will exclude all patients with the outcome prior to the index event. If the start of the time window for the analysis falls some days after the index event, patients will also be excluded if they have the outcome between the index event and the start of the time window.

Measure of Association Analysis

The Measure of Association Analysis calculates and compares the fraction of patients with the selected outcome. The output summary includes: Patients in each Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome in each Cohort (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); and Risk (the fraction of patients in the cohort that have the outcome in the time window, i.e. Patients with Outcome / Patients in Cohort). In addition, Risk Difference (the difference in the risks in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2), Risk Ratio (the ratio of the risks in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2), and Odds Ratio (the ratio of the odds in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2). The bar chart shows the risk of the outcome for the both cohorts.

Survival Analysis

The Kaplan-Meier Analysis estimates probability of the outcome at a respective time interval (daily time interval is used in this analysis). In order to account for the patients who exited the cohort during the analysis period, and therefore should not be included in the analysis, censoring is applied. In this analysis, patients are removed from the analysis (censored) after the last fact in their record.

The output summary includes: Patients in each Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Median Survival (the number of days when the survival drops below 50%; the “-” indicates that survival does

not drop below 50% during the time window); and Survival Probability at End of Time Window (the % survival at the end of the time window). In addition, Log-Rank test, Hazard Ratio and test for Proportionality.

Number of Instances Analysis

The Number of Instances Analysis calculates how many times the outcome occurred in the time window. This analysis includes two additional settings: include patients with zero instances; the definition of an instance.

Selecting to exclude patients with zero instances will remove these patients from the calculations for mean number of instances, standard deviation, or median. The histogram showing the distribution of patients by number of instances will not contain a bar for zero. Alternatively, by selecting to include patients with zero instances, the mean, standard deviation, and median for number of instances will reflect these patients. The histogram will contain a bar for zero patients.

The definition of an instance affects how counts are analyzed. By selecting Date, each calendar date on which any of the terms selected in the outcome are recorded will represent one instance. For example, if the outcome is “Med A or Med B,” and a patient has “Med A” on January 3, then both medications on January 4, then “Med B” on January 6, then that patient is considered to have three instances– January 3, January 4, and January 6. Note that if an outcome occurs across several dates (e.g. Visit: inpatient encounter), then only the start date is tracked for the purpose of counting instances. A patient who begins at stay on January 1, ends that stay on January 3, begins another stay on January 10, and ends that stay on January 15, is considered to have two instances of the outcome.

Selecting Visit as an Instance will count any visit that includes the outcome as one instance, regardless of how many times it occurred. For instance, consider a patient administered an analgesic on each of the three days that make up an inpatient stay following some index event. If analgesic is an outcome, these three administrations will represent only one instance, because all three are associated with the same visit.

The output summary includes: Patients in Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Mean (mean of the counts); Standard Deviation (standard deviation of the counts); Median (median of the counts); and Median (1+ instances) when patients with zero instances included in the analysis. In addition, T-Test statistics testing for the difference between the cohorts is included.

Laboratory Results Analysis

Lab Results can be included in the analysis only for the outcomes that are labs. Only the most recent lab values in the time window are included. For the lab results that are numeric, the outcome summary includes: Patients in Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Mean (mean of the counts); and Standard Deviation (the standard deviation for lab values across patients in the cohort). In addition, T-Test statistics testing for the difference between the cohorts is included.

For the non-numeric lab results, three values are reported: counts of Negative; Positives; and Unknowns. The counts are represented in the bar chart as percentages of the total counts.

Outcome Definitions

Table below outlines the definitions for each outcome and the analysis specifications. For outcome definitions consisting of more than one term, at least one term must match. Please see Appendix C for the text representation of the outcome definitions.

Ascites		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices I85		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.00	Esophageal varices without bleeding
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.01	Esophageal varices with bleeding
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72.9	Hepatic failure, unspecified
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Liver cell carcinoma C22.0		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Sepsis A41		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81		
Outcome definition		

Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41.81	Sepsis due to Enterococcus
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Mortality		
Outcome definition		
Demographics	Deceased	Deceased
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window

Propensity Score Matching

Propensity score matching was performed on all listed characteristics. Characteristics of the cohorts before and after matching are summarized in the table below.

Cohort 1 and cohort 2 patient count before and after propensity score matching		
Cohort	Patient count before matching	Patient count after matching
1 - *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	9,641	6,665
2 - *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	13,394	6,665

Cohort 1 (N = 9,641) and cohort 2 (N = 13,394) characteristics before propensity score matching							
Demographics							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	AI	Age at Index	56.6 +/- 11.8	9,641	100%	<0.001	0.070
2			55.8 +/- 11.6	13,394	100%		
1	M	Male		6,593	68.4%	0.026	0.030
2			9,343	69.8%			
Diagnosis							
Cohort			Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	I21	Acute myocardial infarction		372	3.9%	<0.001	0.139
2			215	1.6%			

1	I50	Heart failure	1,243	12.9%	<0.001	0.173
2			1,026	7.7%		
1	I73	Other peripheral vascular diseases	474	4.9%	<0.001	0.124
2			344	2.6%		
1	I63.5	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries	178	1.8%	<0.001	0.073
2			132	1.0%		
1	J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	1,561	16.2%	<0.001	0.227
2			1,171	8.7%		
1	N18	Chronic kidney disease (CKD)	1,015	10.5%	<0.001	0.161
2			817	6.1%		
1	C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue	132	1.4%	<0.001	0.080
2			78	0.6%		
1	I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease	1,409	14.6%	<0.001	0.218
2			1,042	7.8%		
1	E11	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	2,142	22.2%	<0.001	0.175
2			2,061	15.4%		
1	C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx	132	1.4%	<0.001	0.063
2			97	0.7%		
1	C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs	322	3.3%	<0.001	0.110
2			218	1.6%		
1	C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs	159	1.6%	<0.001	0.058
2			132	1.0%		
1	C40-C41	Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage	11	0.1%	0.438	0.010
2			11	0.1%		
1	C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin	170	1.8%	<0.001	0.058
2			144	1.1%		
1	C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue	27	0.3%	0.002	0.040
2			14	0.1%		
1	C50-C50	Malignant neoplasms of breast (C50)	78	0.8%	0.038	0.027
2			78	0.6%		
1	C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs	35	0.4%	0.014	0.032
2			26	0.2%		
1	C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs	135	1.4%	0.001	0.044
2			125	0.9%		
1	C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract	84	0.9%	<0.001	0.050
2			62	0.5%		
1	C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system	15	0.2%	0.149	0.019
2			12	0.1%		
1	C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands	17	0.2%	0.026	0.029
2			10	0.1%		
1	C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, other secondary and unspecified sites	325	3.4%	<0.001	0.106
2			228	1.7%		
1	C7A-C7A	Malignant neuroendocrine tumors (C7A)	13	0.1%	0.154	0.019
2			10	0.1%		

1	C7B-C7B	Secondary neuroendocrine tumors (C7B)	10	0.1%	0.460	0.010
2			10	0.1%		

Medication

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	4603	furosemide	3,549	36.8%	<0.001	0.593
2			1,654	12.3%		
1	9997	spironolactone	2,530	26.2%	<0.001	0.476
2			1,162	8.7%		
1	6218	lactulose	2,409	25.0%	<0.001	0.545
2			801	6.0%		
1	35619	rifaximin	951	9.9%	<0.001	0.334
2			276	2.1%		
1	8787	propranolol	819	8.5%	<0.001	0.303
2			249	1.9%		
1	7226	nadolol	500	5.2%	<0.001	0.227
2			162	1.2%		
1	20352	carvedilol	688	7.1%	<0.001	0.213
2			345	2.6%		

Laboratory

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.	
1	9050	Bilirubin.total [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	2.5 +/- 4.5	6,980	72.4%	<0.001	0.098
2			2.1 +/- 3.6	5,820	43.5%		
1		1.30 - 0 mg/dL	4,133	42.9%	<0.001	0.435	
2			3,068	22.9%			
1	9045	Albumin [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	3.3 +/- 0.8	6,431	66.7%	<0.001	0.203
2			3.5 +/- 0.8	5,477	40.9%		
1		0 - 3.50 g/dL	4,827	50.1%	<0.001	0.532	
2			3,373	25.2%			
1	9032	INR in Plasma or Blood	1.4 +/- 0.6	6,046	62.7%	<0.001	0.104
2			1.3 +/- 0.5	4,495	33.6%		
1		1.20 - 0 {INR}	3,994	41.4%	<0.001	0.489	
2			2,618	19.5%			

Cohort 1 (N = 6,665) and cohort 2 (N = 6,665) characteristics after propensity score matching

Demographics

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.	
1	AI	Age at Index	56.2 +/- 11.8	6,665	100%	0.349	0.016
2			56.4 +/- 11.7	6,665	100%		
1	M	Male	4,585	68.8%	0.926	0.002	
2			4,590	68.9%			

Diagnosis

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	I21	Acute myocardial infarction	168	2.5%	0.662	0.008
2			176	2.6%		
1	I50	Heart failure	695	10.4%	0.910	0.002
2			691	10.4%		
1	I73	Other peripheral vascular diseases	258	3.9%	0.755	0.005
2			265	4.0%		

1	I63.5	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries	91	1.4%	0.713	0.006
2			96	1.4%		
1	J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	885	13.3%	0.067	0.032
2			958	14.4%		
1	N18	Chronic kidney disease (CKD)	567	8.5%	0.357	0.016
2			597	9.0%		
1	C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue	69	1.0%	0.728	0.006
2			65	1.0%		
1	I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease	754	11.3%	0.068	0.032
2			822	12.3%		
1	E11	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	1,300	19.5%	0.096	0.029
2			1,377	20.7%		
1	C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx	73	1.1%	0.805	0.004
2			76	1.1%		
1	C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs	176	2.6%	0.872	0.003
2			179	2.7%		
1	C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs	94	1.4%	0.942	0.001
2			95	1.4%		
1	C40-C41	Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage	10	0.2%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.2%		
1	C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin	94	1.4%	0.884	0.003
2			96	1.4%		
1	C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue	10	0.2%	0.670	0.007
2			12	0.2%		
1	C50-C50	Malignant neoplasms of breast (C50)	49	0.7%	0.920	0.002
2			50	0.8%		
1	C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs	17	0.3%	0.866	0.003
2			18	0.3%		
1	C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs	81	1.2%	0.323	0.017
2			94	1.4%		
1	C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract	51	0.8%	0.921	0.002
2			52	0.8%		
1	C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system	10	0.2%	0.670	0.007
2			12	0.2%		
1	C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands	10	0.2%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.2%		
1	C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, other secondary and unspecified sites	179	2.7%	0.873	0.003
2			182	2.7%		
1	C7A-C7A	Malignant neuroendocrine tumors (C7A)	10	0.2%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.2%		
1	C7B-C7B	Secondary neuroendocrine tumors (C7B)	10	0.2%	1	<0.001
2			10	0.2%		

Medication

Cohort	Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
--------	-----------	----------	-------------	---------	-----------

1	4603	furosemide	1,617	24.3%	0.543	0.011
2			1,587	23.8%		
1	9997	spironolactone	1,131	17.0%	0.200	0.022
2			1,076	16.1%		
1	6218	lactulose	912	13.7%	0.002	0.054
2			791	11.9%		
1	35619	rifaximin	338	5.1%	0.003	0.052
2			266	4.0%		
1	8787	propranolol	304	4.6%	0.012	0.044
2			246	3.7%		
1	7226	nadolol	192	2.9%	0.084	0.030
2			160	2.4%		
1	20352	carvedilol	323	4.8%	0.655	0.008
2			312	4.7%		

Laboratory

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	9050	Bilirubin.total	4,507	67.6%	<0.001	0.094
2		[Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	4,128	61.9%		
1		1.30 - 0 mg/dL	2,352	35.3%	0.002	0.053
2			2,521	37.8%		
1	9045	Albumin [Mass/volume] in	4,080	61.2%	<0.001	0.142
2		Serum, Plasma or Blood	3,910	58.7%		
1		0 - 3.50 g/dL	2,724	40.9%	0.001	0.060
2			2,921	43.8%		
1	9032	INR in Plasma or Blood	3,781	56.7%	<0.001	0.099
2			3,345	50.2%		
1		1.20 - 0 {INR}	2,162	32.4%	0.063	0.032
2			2,263	34.0%		

Results

Results are summarized in the table below. Analysis was performed on the cohorts after propensity score matching.

1 Ascites				
Risk analysis				
Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome		Risk
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	409		0.061
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	342		0.051
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.010	(0.002, 0.018)	2.517	0.012
Risk Ratio	1.196	(1.040, 1.375)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.209	(1.043, 1.401)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis					
Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	409	--	91.36%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	342	--	92.03%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	2.071	1	0.150		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.111	(0.962, 1.283)	0.291	1	0.590

2 Esophageal varices I85

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	400	0.060	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	207	0.031	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.029	(0.022, 0.036)	8.018	0.000
Risk Ratio	1.932	(1.640, 2.278)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.992	(1.678, 2.364)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	400	--	91.09%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	207	--	94.82%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	48.817	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.803	(1.525, 2.133)	0.005	1	0.941

3 Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	272	0.041	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	140	0.021	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.020	(0.014, 0.026)	6.606	0.000
Risk Ratio	1.943	(1.589, 2.375)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.983	(1.613, 2.438)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	272	--	93.80%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	140	--	96.51%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	32.578	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.796	(1.464, 2.202)	0.193	1	0.660

4 Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	52	0.008	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	16	0.002	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.005	(0.003, 0.008)	4.377	0.000
Risk Ratio	3.250	(1.858, 5.686)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	3.268	(1.864, 5.728)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	52	--	98.86%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	16	--	99.60%	
		χ^2	df	p	
Log-Rank Test	16.551	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	3.022	(1.726, 5.293)	0.173	1	0.677

5 Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	416	0.062	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	258	0.039	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.024	(0.016, 0.031)	6.246	0.000
Risk Ratio	1.612	(1.386, 1.876)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.653	(1.410, 1.938)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	416	--	90.72%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	258	--	93.68%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	25.803	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.492	(1.277, 1.742)	0.086	1	0.770

6 Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	354	0.053	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	228	0.034	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.019	(0.012, 0.026)	5.341	0.000
Risk Ratio	1.553	(1.319, 1.827)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.584	(1.336, 1.877)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window		
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	354	--	92.08%		
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	228	--	94.47%		
		χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	18.106	1	0.000			
		Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.432	(1.213, 1.692)	0.938	1	0.333	

7 Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	67	0.010	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	22	0.003	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.007	(0.004, 0.010)	4.786	0.000
Risk Ratio	3.045	(1.884, 4.924)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	3.066	(1.892, 4.969)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	67	--	98.51%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	22	--	99.46%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	19.097	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	2.796	(1.727, 4.526)	0.002	1	0.966

8 Liver cell carcinoma C22.0

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	113	0.017	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	96	0.014	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.003	(-0.002, 0.007)	1.185	0.236
Risk Ratio	1.177	(0.899, 1.542)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.180	(0.897, 1.552)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	113	--	97.38%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	96	--	97.56%	
		χ^2	df	p	
Log-Rank Test	0.315	1	0.575		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.081	(0.824, 1.419)	0.001	1	0.981

9 Sepsis A41

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk		
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	353	0.053		
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	187	0.028		
		95% CI	z	p	
Risk Difference	0.025	(0.018, 0.032)	7.293	0.000	
Risk Ratio	1.888	(1.586, 2.246)	N/A	N/A	
Odds Ratio	1.937	(1.617, 2.321)	N/A	N/A	

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window		
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	353	--	91.96%		
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	187	--	95.35%		
		χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	38.496	1	0.000			
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p	
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.740	(1.458, 2.078)	0.574	1	0.449	

10 Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	10	0.002	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	10	0.002	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0	(-0.001, 0.001)	0	1
Risk Ratio	1	(0.416, 2.401)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1	(0.416, 2.404)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	10	--	99.86%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	10	--	99.95%	
		χ^2	df	p	
Log-Rank Test	1.628	1	0.202		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	2.717	(0.548, 13.464)	0.572	1	0.449

11 Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk		
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	78	0.012		
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	25	0.004		
		95% CI	z	p	
Risk Difference	0.008	(0.005, 0.011)	5.243	0.000	
Risk Ratio	3.120	(1.991, 4.889)	N/A	N/A	
Odds Ratio	3.145	(2.002, 4.941)	N/A	N/A	

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	78	--	98.28%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	25	--	99.36%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	22.996	1	0.000		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	2.866	(1.827, 4.497)	0.594	1	0.441

12 Mortality

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	1,101	0.165	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	1,143	0.171	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	-0.006	(-0.019, 0.006)	-0.972	0.331
Risk Ratio	0.963	(0.893, 1.039)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	0.956	(0.873, 1.047)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	1,101	--	77.69%	
2 *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23	6,665	1,143	--	74.95%	
		χ^2	df	p	
Log-Rank Test	9.080	1	0.003		
		Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.881	(0.811, 0.957)	0.183	1	0.669

Appendix A – Text Representation of the Cohorts Definition

This section lists all terms used in the definitions of the two cohorts.

Query Criteria for Cohort 1 (query name: *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23)

Patients must have:

Age (Age) (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence)).

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Wilson's disease (UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01); or
Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01); or
Cholangitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0); or
Primary biliary cirrhosis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3); or
Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); or
Viral hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19); or
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

All the following must be satisfied:

Alc CIR: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3) (at least 18 years old at event).

Group 1B: Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR

Patients must have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Group 2A: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3) (at least 18 years old at event).

Group 2B: Any instance of Group 2B occurred on or before any instance of Group 2A

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2); or
Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41); or
Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0); or
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72); or
Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85); or
Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7); or
Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Query Criteria for Cohort 2 (query name: *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23)

Patients must have:

Age (Age) (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence)).

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Wilson's disease (UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01); or
Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01); or
Cholangitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0); or
Primary biliary cirrhosis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3); or
Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); or
Viral hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19); or
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81).

All the following must be satisfied:

Alc CIR: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3) (at least 18 years old at event).

Group 1B: Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Group 2A: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3) (at least 18 years old at event).

Group 2B: Any instance of Group 2B occurred on or before any instance of Group 2A

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2); or
Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41); or
Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0); or
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72); or
Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85); or
Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7); or
Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Appendix B – Text Representation of the Analysis Setup

This section contains the Index Event definition for each cohort.

The index event for Cohort 1 (query name: *Alc CIR PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23) is defined as the following:

All the following must be satisfied:

Alc CIR: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3) (at least 18 years old at event).

Group 1B: Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR

Patients must have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or

esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or

lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or

pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or

Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

The index event for Cohort 2 (query name: *Alc CIR No PPI 4.03-19 RN 1.13.23) is defined as the following:

All the following must be satisfied:

Alc CIR: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3) (at least 18 years old at event).

Group 1B: Any instance of Group 1B occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Alc CIR

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or

esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or

lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or

pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or

Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Appendix C – Text Representation of the Outcomes Definition

This analysis includes the following outcomes:

Ascites

Patients must have:

Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Esophageal varices I85

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85).

Esophageal varicies w/o bleeding I85.0

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices without bleeding (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.00).

Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices with bleeding (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.01).

Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72

Patients must have:

Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72).

Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9

Patients must have:

Hepatic failure, unspecified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72.9).

Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7

Patients must have:

Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7).

Liver cell carcinoma C22.0

Patients must have:

Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0).

Sepsis A41

Patients must have:

Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41).

Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81

Patients must have:

Sepsis due to Enterococcus (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41.81).

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2

Patients must have:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2).

Mortality

Patients must have:

Deceased (Deceased).